

SELECTION OF METHODS FOR TRANSFERRING TRAINS FROM ONE-AND TWO-WAY SECTIONS

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Breaks caused by unexpected technical reasons on one-way sections lead to a complete stoppage of train traffic. Therefore, the options for organizing the movement of trains on these sections are considered after breaks.

After a break in one-way sections, it is possible to achieve an increase in the transfer volume of the section by the following methods:

- package organization of train movement;
- Organization of train movement in the form of dual trains.

The delay of such trains in relation to the specified time or arrival time zone leads to significant financial losses for rail transport. Therefore, trains are offered to provide reserves for them in the rationing of elements of the movement graph.

The transfer volume of peregons to which driving locomotives are applied is determined depending on the operating system of auxiliary locomotives. The feasibility of applying driving locomotives on these sections is based on special feasibility calculations.

Reducing the time to resume movement after breaks caused by unexpected technical reasons on two-way sections and reducing train interception can be done by using the dual-track train transfer method and increasing the number of trains on the package in the package in the package method of organizing movement.

In this case, the movement of dual trains on two-way sections after the planned break is carried out by connecting two or more single trains at peregons or stations.

Dual trains diverge after passing through the repaired passage and pass (move) like regular trains in the later passages.

For the transfer of dual trains, it is imperative to establish time norms for connecting and separating trains. The total time of connecting trains is 8 minutes, and the break time is 6 minutes. In turn, the running time of trains on passage increases by 14 minutes.

Determination of train delay train hours.

The total delay time of trains for unexpected technical reasons is determined by the sum of:

- the passage of trains (one train) along the right track with an average interval;
- waiting for double trains in the package in the opposite direction to release passage;
- separation of composition after passing through the repaired section;
- restoring the normal operation of the section.

The number of source data required to calculate the delay indicators of freight trains includes:

- the reason for the incident is the duration of the recovery of the action after the assessment by the inspection commission. $-t_{rec}$;
- trains are the average interval between freight trains in odd and even directions on the movement graph;
- one of the main roads closed indefinitely during the passage movement graph period;
- the interval between trains in odd and even directions of movement;
- packing coefficient $-\alpha_{pack}$.

Trains for one-way peregon without delay the sum of train-hours is equal to the following.

$$\sum N_{freight}t = t_{break} \frac{N_{freight}}{24} + t_{break} \frac{N_{freight}}{24} \left(t_{break} \frac{N_{freight}}{24} + 1 \right) \cdot 0,5 \left(T_{period}^{delay} - \frac{N_{freight}}{24} \right), \quad (1)$$

There T_{davr}^{in} – interception train transfer interval,

$$T_{period}^{delay} = \frac{t_{rec}}{N} = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{T_{period}} \frac{N}{24}}, \quad (2)$$

Trains for two-way peregon the sum of the delay train-hours is determined by the following formula:

$$\sum N_{freight}t = \frac{N_{freight}}{24} (T_{period}^i - I) \frac{t_{break}}{2}, \quad (3)$$

These analytical dependencies ((1), (2)) provide an opportunity to calculate train delays under ideal conditions (on a parallel graph and when train flows are uniform).

Conclusion

One of the cases in which, for unexpected technical reasons, time losses are common outside the schedule of train traffic on one-or two-tway sections. In order to normalize time losses in the movement of trains in the event of such situations, methods of package organization and transfer of the movement of trains in the form of double trains were considered.

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